

Leaf water potential (LWP) of upland rice breeding lines and varieties in an irrigated field in Gazipur, Bangladesh, 1988.

Variety or line	LWP (MPa)
BR4290-3-1-10	- 0.75
BR4290-3-3-5	- 1.24
BR1888-29-2-2-3	- 1.00
BR1888-29-2-3-4	- 1.00
BR1890-12-2-1-1	- 1.11
BR1890-1-1-1-2	- 1.14
BR20	- 0.90
BR21	- 0.92
<i>F-test</i>	184.42**
LSD (0.05)	0.04

Stress tolerance — excess water

Germination and seedling development of floating rice at different soil moisture regimes

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Farmers usually dry seed floating rices before the onset of monsoon rains. In certain years, when the monsoon is early, dry seeding is not possible. Also, dry seeding is followed by drought, and farmers may have to replant a wet seeded rice.

We studied germination and growth of floating rice under different moisture regimes at crop establishment. Dry seeds and pregerminated seeds of Pin Gaew 56, a Thai floating rice, were planted at 100 seeds/tray in 25- × 33- × 10-cm plastic trays filled with 7 kg Maahas clay soil. Four soil moisture regimes were applied, with three replications (see table).

The pregerminated seeds emerged first. However, differences in percentage

Emergence of Pin Gaew 56 seedlings under different soil moisture regimes.^a IRRI greenhouse, 1990.

Soil moisture	Emergence (%) at 7 DAS	
	Dry seed	Pregerminated seed
Field capacity	98 a	98 a
Saturated	95 ab	95 ab
2 cm clear water	67 c	87 b
2 cm muddy water	71 c	74 c

^aIn a column, values followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

of emergence between dry seeds and pregerminated seeds 7 d after sowing (DAS) were small. Field capacity and saturated soil moisture favored seedling emergence. As little as 2 cm excess water significantly decreased emergence. Pregerminated seeds emerged poorly in muddy water.

Growth and development were vigorous at field capacity and at saturation (see figure). However, seedlings from pregerminated seeds tended to grow and develop better in saturated soil than at field capacity. Standing 2-cm-deep water significantly retarded seedling growth and development.

The effects were more-pronounced in seedlings from dry seed than from pregerminated seed. Muddy water at seeding did not have much effect on growth and development at later stages because the water cleared within 24 h.

The results indicate that field capacity or saturated soil moisture regime is favorable for germination, growth, and development of both dry and pregerminated seeds. Broadcasting dry seeds of floating rice is recommended, but pregerminated seeds could be an alternative in very wet or extremely low areas where rainwater accumulates during sowing. ■

Shoot and root dry weight of rice seedlings germinated under different soil moisture regimes. IRRI greenhouse, 1990.

Stress tolerance — adverse temperature

Screening rice cultivars at reproductive stage for low temperature tolerance in western Nepal

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Injury due to low temperature is a major constraint to improvement of rice production in the 1,000-2,000 m high areas of Nepal. No improved variety has yet been developed for elevations above 1,400 m.

In 1987 and 1988, we evaluated rice cultivars at three altitudes. The materials

were from IRRI; the National Rice Improvement Programme (NRIP), Parwanipur; Department of Agricultural Botany (DOAB); and local germplasm collected from 1,000-2,300 m altitudes in the western hills.

In 1987, the materials were evaluated at Tapu (1,000 m), Lumle (1,400 m), and Chhomro (2,000 m) to identify varietal differences in low temperature tolerance and altitude and the highest limit of varietal adaptation. In 1988, materials identified as promising from the 1987 trials were assessed at Tapu. Sera (1,250 m), and Lumle. Test cultivars were planted in rows in 1.2-m² plots, at 20- ×

20-cm spacing. Low temperature tolerance was measured in terms of spikelet sterility and yield. No serious stress was observed before the preanthesis period.

The 1987 yields showed strong varietal differences with altitude. Eleven genotypes produced grain at 2,000 m (Table 1). At 1,400 m, 17 genotypes produced grain. Minimum (night) temperatures ranged from 12.9 to 16.9 °C and maximum (day) temperatures from 23.5 to 23.9 °C. Water temperatures of the higher altitude sites were cooler (18.5-22.1 °C) than water temperatures at 1,000 m (23.9-25.3 °C) at anthesis. Water tem-

perature at anthesis at the 1,000-m site appears to be warmer than the critical limit for low temperature stress-induced sterility. We believe sterility and poor yield performance were associated with low temperature stress.

Yields in 1988 were higher than in 1987 (Table 2). Fifteen varieties produced some yield at 1,400 m. Spikelet sterility in these cultivars was low. Six exotic lines also showed some low temperature tolerance. But at 1,400 m, more than half the varieties evaluated failed to set grain.

We think the better performance of most of the low temperature-tolerant

varieties at 1,400 m can be associated with the relatively warmer water temperatures at anthesis in 1988 (22.1-21.2 °C) than in 1987 (19.0-18.5 °C).

At 1,250 m, 23 genotypes produced some yield. At 1,000 m, almost all varieties showed no symptoms of low temperature stress. Yields of IR7167-33-2-3-3 and NR15579-24-2 were best at lower altitudes. Varieties that perform better in the high hills (Chhomro, Ghara, Himali, Banahun, Raksali, and Seto Bhakunde) had comparatively poor yields in the lower elevations.

Local varieties Chhomro, Ghandruk, Himali Marshi, Ghara, Banahun, and Seto Bhakunde were identified as having low temperature tolerance. They could be used in breeding programs or extended into areas lacking adapted cultivars. ■

Table 1. Performance of low temperature-tolerant rice cultivars at 3 altitudes (1000-2000 m).^a Nepal, 1987.

Cultivar	2000 m		1400 m		1000 m	
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Spikelet sterility (%)
Ghandruk local	6.0	1	2.4	1	3.2	1
Himali Marshi	4.8	1	2.5	1	1.3	1
Ghara Local	4.0	1	3.7	1	2.9	1
Chhomro local (check)	3.7	1	3.2	3	0.5	1
Kalo Dhan	2.7	5	-	-	6.8	1
Banahun local	1.8	3	2.4	1	3.2	1
Seto Bhakunde	1.6	5	2.3	5	2.9	1
RP1442-8-2-1-2	1.2	7	-	-	3.2	1
Jumli Marshi	1.2	7	-	9	0.5	1
NR1066-1	0.8	7	-	-	0.5	1
(NRCTN, 1987 ^b) (n = 110)	(0-6)	(1-9)	(0-3.7)	(1-9)	(0.5-8.3)	(1-5)

^a Gram yield adjusted to 12% moisture. ^b Spikelet sterility at growth stage 8-9 rated by this scale: 1 = <1%, 3 = 1-5%, 5 = 5-25%, 7 = 25-50%. 9 = 50-100% spikelet sterility. ^c National Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery.

Table 2. Performance of low temperature-tolerant rice varieties at 3 altitudes.^a Nepal, 1988.

Genotype	1400 m		1250 m		1000 m	
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Spikelet sterility (%)
Chhomro local (check)	7.6	1	3.7	1	2.5	1
Ghara	6.1	3	2.6	1	2.0	1
Himali Marshi	6.0	1	5.0	1	1.7	1
Banahun local	5.4	1	2.5	1	1.8	1
NR10073-167-3-1	4.7	3	3.6	1	3.1	1
IR8866-393-14-2	4.3	3	5.1	1	4.4	1
IR7167-33-2-3-3	4.0	3	5.1	1	5.5	1
NR15579-24-2	3.3	3	2.2	3	5.2	3
RP1442-8-2-1-2	2.9	3	4.1	1	2.1	1
Raksali (check)	2.9	3	4.6	1	1.7	1
Seto Bhakunde	1.9	7	1.7	1	4.4	1
IR9202-6-1-1	1.9	3	3.5	1	2.0	1
Barkhe-2	1.5	5	1.8	1	3.2	1
Pokhareli Masino	1.4	7	3.4	1	4.2	1
BG400-1	1.0	7	3.1	1	2.5	1
NRCTN, 1988 (n = 33)	(0-7.6)	(1-9)	(1.6-5.5)	(1-5)	(1.2-5.6)	(1-3)

^a Grain yield adjusted to 12% moisture. Spikelet sterility (at growth stage 8-9) rated by the scale in Table 1.

Integrated germplasm improvement — irrigated

CICA8 and ITA222, new rice varieties for irrigated areas of Mbo Plain in West Cameroon

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Mbo Plain, an area of about 30,000 ha, is in the West Province of Cameroon at 700 m altitude. About 10,000 ha are potentially suitable for rice cultivation, but only 210 ha are currently under irrigated production.

Major constraints are the disease susceptibility and grain characteristics of the currently grown variety Tainan V.

Although it is susceptible to leaf blast (BI) at early vegetative stages, Tainan V has the ability to recover and yields close to 4 t/ha in farmers' fields (Table 1). However, its short and bold grain, chalkiness, and cooking quality are not favored by urban consumers, causing difficulty in marketing.